

EFFECTIVENESS OF REMINISCENCE COUNSELLING THERAPY ON LONELINESS BEHAVIOUR AMONG OLDER ADULTS IN SOKOTO CENTRAL CONSTITUENCY, SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The research investigated the effectiveness of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in reducing maladaptive behaviour of loneliness by older adult population in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State. The study used quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test designs. The population of the study consists of older adults affected with loneliness behaviour in Sokoto Central Constituency. The sample size of 40 older adult participants was purposively selected to form Experimental /Treatment Group. Participants received reminiscence therapy session one in each week for 12 weeks. Each therapy session lasted for 80 minutes in length. Two instruments were used for data collection during pre-test and post-test assessment periods. Each participant completed the instruments before and immediately after the intervention. The data obtained from pre-test and post-test results with the help of research instruments were compared to determine the effectiveness level and indeed the differences in quality of life of older adult before and after the reminiscence counselling intervention. Paired sample t-test was used to test the formulated hypotheses with the help of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 20. The findings of the study revealed that, the act of loneliness of the respondents significantly reduced after they were exposed to Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT). The findings revealed that RCT proved to be effective among male older adults in Sokoto central constituency. The counselling intervention finally, revealed that Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) helps in improving the quality of life of the older adult. Therefore, RCT counselling should be used in managing older adults with maladaptive behaviour of loneliness in Sokoto Central Constituency.

Key words: Reminiscence therapy & Loneliness Behaviour

Introduction

Loneliness among the elderly paves ways for many psychological disorders. It makes them vulnerable if an effective intervention is not provided. Loneliness

proves to be the most common cause of elderly mentally unbalanced states such as depression and intense despair, which is an unpleasant, negative, frustrating, and painful personal experience, often

capable of triggering a feeling of boredom, depression, and anxiety in a person (Hsieh & Wang, 2003). The findings indicate that loneliness is not synonymous with living alone.

Loneliness occurs when an important and meaningful social interaction in terms of quantity or quality is diminished with aging. The effects of art therapy on older adults with loneliness include maintenance and improvement of cognitive function, assistance in cognitive function evaluation, provision of reminiscence methods, and improvement of agitation, uneasiness, aggressiveness, and confusion (Chancellor, Duncan, & Chatterjee, 2014).

Reminiscence is a process that occurs in stages, involving the Recalling of early life events and previous interpersonal interactions (Dempsey, Murphy, Cooney, Casey, O'Shea, Devane and Hunter, 2014). Alternatively, reminiscence may be seen as how recollections and interpretations of past life events, typically those that occurred in the distant past, are generated in the present (Gonzalez, Mayordomo, Torres, Sales, & Melendez, 2015). Reminiscence is an independent nursing intervention known as reminiscence therapy, which is defined under the Nursing Intervention Classification system as an intervention that utilizes the recollection of past

thoughts, feelings, and events to enhance the happiness and quality of life of an individual or to assist that individual to adapt to his or her present situation (McCloskey & Bulechek 2000).

Three main types of reminiscence therapy have been identified: simple reminiscence, life review, and life-review therapy (Pinquart & Forstmeier, 2012). Simple reminiscence is a recollection of positive autobiographical events to encourage positive emotions. Life review focuses on both positive and negative memories, encompassing the entire life span (Haber, 2006). Life-review therapy helps patients with a diagnosis of depression to reframe negative memories in a positive way, they restructuring beliefs, and building self-efficacy and coping skills. However, these definitions are often merged (Webster, Bohlmeijer, & Westerhof, 2010). For the purpose of this study, reminiscence work is an intervention that uses recall of past events, feelings, and thoughts usually with the help of prompts such as old photographs, newspaper clippings, videos of old films, music and archived sound recordings, or household and other familiar items from the past, to enable people to talk about experience and life events that took place usually in the distant past (Webster, 2003).

Reminiscence therapy reduces social isolation of loneliness and

improves cognitive performance, self-esteem, life satisfaction and self-worth levels. Sharing memories with others and reminiscence help people to attain their integrity (Hsieh & Wang, 2003). It may also be a tool for individual matching with unpleasant past. In addition, reminiscence increases elderly attention to themselves and helps them in coping with conflicts and absence of this period, reconstruction of life stories and evaluations of positive and negative experiences (Bryant, Smart & King, 2005). The roles of reminiscence for elderly individuals include: Promoting self-understanding, preservation of individual and collective memories, overcoming physical and world limitations, creating opportunities for understanding human law and strengthening coping strategies by minimizing rate of loneliness (Chiang, 2009).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical basic of this research is the Activity theory which came in response to disengagement theory (Wadensten, 2003). Activity theory states that ageism and discrimination causes older individuals to withdraw from society, and disengagement is not a choice freely chosen. The basic idea of Activity theory is that individuals do not fundamentally change when they grow

older; rather they are the same middle-aged person with just more physical limitations due to age. The ideology of activity theory is that for individuals to be happy in old age they need to continue to meet developmental tasks. If the senior citizens meet these developmental tasks they are more likely to be happy. It is thought that the best way for seniors to “age successfully” is for them to continue to maintain an active lifestyle and partake in social and physical activities similar to those of younger years. The more activity, the better one will do. In comparison to disengagement theory, there is no cognitive shift. For individuals to remain happy they should continue into age the same life they have always lived. When individuals do not continue to partake in the same level of physical and social activity, they could not be said to have “aged successful”.

Statement of Problem

Ageing or senescence is a period like any other stage of human development such as infancy, childhood and adulthood. It is a universal process which affects each and every human being globally, physically, and psychologically. Ageing is a process that begins with conception practically, although ageing is associated with a phase in life when the body functioning begins to decline and is characterized by loss of adaptive

responses to life stressors as well as higher level of vulnerability to risk in term of age related diseases. The mental disorders of elderly people, especially the high incidence of geriatric anxiety, loneliness, emotional blame and depression, have become an issue of increasing concern due to the rapid population growth rate of the older adult. Ageing is an unavoidable reality of life which takes place at different dimensions, such as social, behavioural, psychological, morphological and otherwise. In addition to physical challenges, mental disorder is the commonest problem surrounding the period. The identified problems associated with old age are; feelings of loneliness, feelings of unwantedness, feeling of inadequacy, obsolescence of skill and at severe stage dementia of various degree. These directly or indirectly affect the quality and quantity of the cognitive functioning of the aged individual. Quality of life is about needs and the satisfaction of one's needs, values and preferences, which naturally change with the development of a human personality (Cevela, Kalvach, Čeledová and Sociální 2013). With life expectancy increasing, it is becoming more and more important to consider the factors that can positively influence ageing and quality of life at old age.

Since loneliness is a psychological disorder, little contribution is expected from the physical treatment of medical practitioners. Maladaptive behaviours usually require counselling intervention of social therapists in the field of psychology and counselling. Therapeutic interventions like Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT), Cognitive Therapy, Assertive Therapy and Reminiscence Therapy are applied to deal with various mental disorders. As a psychosocial intervention, reminiscence is frequently applied to elderly patients and to those being treated for dementia (Yen & Lin, 2018). Gonzalez, Mayordomo, Torres, Sales and Melendez (2015) noted that reminiscence therapy involves the discussion of past activities, events, and experiences, usually with the aid of prompts such as photographs, household and other familiar items from the past, music, and archived sound recordings.

It has being observed that, loneliness is one of the common maladaptive behaviours affecting aged individuals in Sokoto Central Constituency. The affected individuals might have lost either attachments of intimate friend, wife or work engagement. The condition which mostly called for isolation before alternatives are been provided, otherwise negative emotional thought of related loss of

attachments make them vulnerable to many geriatric diseases. The research on older adult related to loneliness and its intervention has not been identified by any researcher in Sokoto central constituency despite the growing number of aged individuals vulnerable to old age disease (Alzheimer). Therefore the present study attempt to assess the effectiveness of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in reducing maladaptive behaviour of loneliness among older adult population in Sokoto Central constituency (Sokoto North, Sokoto South, Wamakko, Kware Binji Silame, Tangaza and Gudu llocal government areas) , Sokoto State.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the effectiveness of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) on treatment of loneliness among Older Adults in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State
2. To identify the effectiveness of Reminiscence Therapy (RCT) on treatment of loneliness among Male Older Adults in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State
3. To determine the effectiveness of Reminiscence Counselling (RCT) therapy on improving the quality of life among the elderly in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State

Research Hypotheses

1. **HO₁** There is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in treatment of loneliness among Older Adults in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State
2. **HO₂** There is no significant effect of Reminiscence Therapy (RCT) in treatment of loneliness among Male Older Adults in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State
3. **HO₃** There is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling (RCT) therapy in improving quality of life of the elderly in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State

Methodology

The study used quasi experimental research of pre and post-test control design. Participants of the study were all individuals aged between 65 to 85 years old. The sample of the study consisted of two groups; an experimental and a control group of 20 aged individuals. The experimental group was exposed to 14 sessions of reminiscence intervention therapy for 14 weeks; one session per week. Participants were randomly assigned to experimental and control group using balloting to minimize the rate of blame of subjectivity. Therefore, they determine their fate of being in either experimental or control group. The study area comprises all the local

government areas within Sokoto Central Constituency but the population of the study is limited to older adults with maladaptive behavior of loneliness in the study area. Every older adult with maladaptive behavior of loneliness stood the chance of being selected as part of the sample.

Two instruments were used;

- 1 World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire (WOQLOQ) by (WHO, 1998)
- 2 The revised University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA) Loneliness Scale by (Russell, Peplau, & Cutrona, 1996).

World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire (WOQLOQ): This scale includes two parts: the first part is devoted to background information and demographic questions including name, family name, age, sex, marital status, economic status, disease history, and so on. The second part consists of 26 questions that measure the quality of life in four domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships and Social environment (World Health Organization, 1998). Questions are 5-multiple choices, and their Scoring is between 1 and 5 points. Since 1996, validity and reliability of questionnaire has been done in countries and different cultures by World Health Organization.

Bonomi et al, in internal reliability of this test reported coefficient 0.83 to 0.95. Also Natalie in chronic group, reported that reliability of this test is 0.90 and in group of normal individuals is 0.86(Williams, 2000). In Iran, Rahimi (2002) estimated its reliability coefficient at 0.89.

Research on loneliness has been hindered by the lack of a simple and reliable assessment technique. The development of the UCLA Loneliness Scale, a short, 20-item general measure of loneliness is reported. The measure has high internal consistency (coefficient alpha = .96) and a test-retest correlation over a two-month period of .73. Concurrent and preliminary construct validity are indicated by correlations with self-reports of current loneliness and related emotional states, and by volunteering for a “loneliness clinic”.

The data obtained from pre-test and post-test result with the help of research instruments were compared to determine the effectiveness of reminiscence counselling therapy on loneliness and indeed the differences in quality of life of older adults before and after the reminiscence counselling intervention. Independent t-test and paired sample t-test were used to test the formulated hypotheses with the help of Statistical Package for Social Science

(SPSS) Version 20 and result obtained are as follows.

Findings

HO₁ There is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in treatment of loneliness among Older Adult in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State.

The scores of the respondents in relation to this hypothesis were subjected to pair t-test analysis as presented in table 1 below;

Table 1: Reminiscence Counselling Therapy

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	df	Decision
RT Pre /	-	1.08573	-	.000	19	Rejected
RT Pos	2.04750		8.434			

p < 0.05

Table 1 shows the paired Sample t-test result of (M = -204750, SD = 1.08573, t = -8 434, df. 19 and p-Value =.000). Thus, the respondents loneliness level reduced as a result of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) intervention received. Because the realized p-Value is less than .05 level of significance. This showed that there is significant reduction of loneliness among the respondents due to counselling intervention. Therefore, the **HO₁** which stated that, there is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in the treatment of loneliness among older adult

in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State is hereby rejected.

HO₂ There is no significant effect of Reminiscence Therapy (RCT) in treatment of loneliness among Older Male Adult in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State

Table 2: Reminiscence Counselling Therapy among Male Older Adult.

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	df	Decision
RT Pre /	-2.04750	1.08573	-8.434	.000	19	Rejected
RT Pos						

p < 0.05

Table 2 above shows the paired Sample t-test result of (M = -204750, SD = 1.08573, t = -8 434, df. 19 and p-Value =.000). Thus, the respondents' loneliness level reduced as a result of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) intervention received. Because the realized p-Value is less than .05 level of significance. This showed that there is significant reduction of loneliness among the respondents due to counselling intervention. Therefore, the **HO₂** which stated that, there is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in the treatment of loneliness among older male adult in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State is hereby rejected.

HO₃ There is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling (RCT) therapy in improving quality of life of the

elderly in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	df	Decision
QL Pre / QL Pos	-2.82830	21233	-59570	.000	19	Rejected

p < 0.05

Table 3 above shows the paired Sample t-test result of (M = -2 82830, SD = 21233, $t = -59570$, $df. 19$ and p -Value = .000). Thus, the respondents' quality of life (QL) improved as a result of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) intervention received. Because the realized p -Value is less than .05 level of significance. This showed that there is significant improvement in quality of life among the respondents due to reminiscence counselling intervention. Therefore, the H_{01} which stated that, there is no significant effect of Reminiscence Counselling Therapy (RCT) in improving quality of life among the older adult in Sokoto Central constituency, Sokoto State is hereby rejected.

Discussion

The finding of hypothesis number one and two revealed that there is significant effect of RCT in the treatment of loneliness after comparing the mean scores of pre-test and post-test among the older adult in Sokoto Central

constituency, Sokoto State . The null hypothesis was rejected on the ground that the p-value of .000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. This clearly indicates that there is significant effect of reminiscence counselling therapy in the treatment of loneliness among the older adult in Sokoto Central constituency.

This finding concurs with Zhou (2011) who studied 125 older adults living in eight randomly selected communities in Changsha city, divided into experimental and control groups. The former received six weeks of reminiscence therapy on the topics of self-introduction, recalling old songs, sharing old photos, recalling happy moments growing up, recalling lifetime achievements, and future expectations. The topics chosen deliberately respected the cultural background of the elderly involved. After this their mental health was assessed using three measures: Geriatric Depression Scale, Self-Esteem Scale and the Affect Balance Scale. The study found that reminiscence therapy significantly reduced the symptoms of depression and improved affect balance; however, there was no difference in the self-esteem of the experimental and control groups.

The finding also concurs with the research conducted by Meléndez-Moral, Charco-Ruiz, Mayordomo-Rodriguez, and Sales-Galan , (2013) on

the extent of integrative reminiscence intervention effect using a quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test and control group of patients on the waiting list with 34 healthy elderly people attending eight sessions. The researchers found that in comparison to the control group, the intervention group demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in depression symptoms and a significant improvement in self-esteem, integrity, life satisfaction, and psychological well-being.

However, the finding of the third hypothesis which reveals significant improvement in quality of life among the respondents due to reminiscence counselling intervention concurs with recent study by Lök, Bademli, and Selçuk-Tosun (2018). It found positive effects of reminiscence therapy on reducing depression symptoms and on increasing quality of life in older patients with dementia. It is also in line with Antony, (2005) research which assessed the quality of life before and after laughter therapy in old age homes. 30 samples were selected and Quality of Life (QOL) tool was used. Intervention Laughter therapy was given for a week. After the intervention there was significant difference in quality of life. Statistical significance in all domains. Findings suggested that reminiscence therapy was effective for old age people.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the act of loneliness of the respondents significantly reduced after they were exposed to Reminiscence counselling Therapy (RCT). Therefore, RCT counselling should be used in managing older adults with maladaptive behavior of loneliness. The findings further revealed that RCT proved to be effective among male older adults in Sokoto central constituency. The counselling intervention finally, revealed that Reminiscence counselling Therapy (RCT) helps in improving the quality of life of the older adult.

Recommendations

1. RCT interventions should be used by counsellors and other social workers in managing older adults with loneliness in Sokoto Central Constituency and beyond.
2. RCT interventions should also be used by counsellors and other social workers in improving quality of life of the older adults in Sokoto Central Constituency and beyond.

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